

Pascale Jablonka

Happily collaborating with *F. Rérat*, *D. Spérone-Longin*, *A. Aragon-Salamanca*,
N. Cantale, *F. Combes*, *F. Courbin*, *V. Desai*, *R. Finn*, *P. Hudelot*, *G. de Lucia*, *M. Krips*,
G. Rudnick, *D. Zaritsky* & the *EDisCS* collaboration

- Quenching time scales ?
EDisCS (ESO Distant Cluster Survey)
- Fueling star formation – molecular gas:
SEEDisCS (Spatially extended EDisCS)

How easy is it to identify/characterize clusters for evolutionary studies ?

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COSMOS @ $z \sim 0.52$

zCOMOS 20k
Knobel et al. 2012

$I < 23\text{mag}$

When mass, magnitude cuts make a difference

a well populated red sequence is a reference

EDisCS: ESO Distant Cluster Survey

VLT B, V, R, I, J & K follow-up of the highest surface brightness cluster candidates in the Las Campanas Distant Cluster Survey (LCDCS, 90×1.5 degrees, Gonzales et 2001)

@ $0.45 < z_{\text{est}} < 0.55$ and $0.75 < z_{\text{est}} < 0.85$

16 clusters : $400 < \sigma < 1100$ km/s

@ $0.4 \lesssim z \lesssim 0.8$

20-50 spectroscopic cluster members within R200

White et al., 2005

Very clear structures, well populated red sequences

FORS2 FoV

$z=0.48$, $\sigma=687\text{km/s}$

Very clear structures, well populated red sequences

FORS2 FoV

$z=0.52$, $\sigma=710\text{km/s}$

- Quenching time scales ?

EDisCS (ESO Distant Cluster Survey)

EDisCS: ESO Distant Cluster Survey

VLT/FORS2
7x7 arcmin
B,V,R,I

- 10 clusters @ $0.5 \leq z \leq 0.8$
- 172 cluster + 96 field *spiral* galaxies
- Coverage up to (1-2)R200

FORS2

FIREDEC

HST

EDCSNJ1227541-1138174

EDCSNJ1228001-1136095

EDCSNJ1054416-1247375

EDCSNJ1216447-1201282

spatial resolution

*deconvolution
of V and I images*

*from ground-based
to
space-like*

Cantale et al.
2016 A&A 589, 82

FORS2

FIREDEC

HST

EDCSNJ1227541-1138174

EDCSNJ1228001-1136095

EDCSNJ1054416-1247375

EDCSNJ1216447-1201282

we isolate the disc structures by removing the bulge zones of influence

no prior on profile shapes

Cantale et al.
2016, A&A, 589, 82

Hubble type – disc color relations

comparison clusters / field

Hubble type – disc color relations *comparison clusters / field*

Observations:

irrespective of z , mass of the group/cluster, or galaxy position in phase-space diagramme

Quenching caught in the act

- Galaxy on red sequence with reddened disc
- Galaxy not on red sequence with normal field-like disc
- Galaxy not on red sequence with reddened disc

---- : Maraston et al. (2003) models

Quenching caught in the act

Full quenching acts
on a few Gyr
(long) timescales

---- : Maraston et al. (2003) models

Evolution with time

&

Spatial transformation

CFHT/MEGACAM

u,g,r,i,z

60x60 arcmin

CFHT/WIRCAM K_s

Cluster ID	z_{cl}	σ_{cl} [km/s]	R_{200} [Mpc]	FOV / R_{200}
cl1301.7-1139	0.4828	687	3.65	8.23
cl1301.7-1139a	0.3969	391	2.44	12.27
cl1411.1-1148	0.5195	709	3.55	8.46

SEEDisCS

- Catching quenching in the act:
how much is in preprocessing?
- Getting all cosmic densities in a consistent and homegenous way: from the highest to the lowest densities

Density maps

Z=0.48

CL1301.7-1139

Z=0.52

CL1411.1-1148

$\text{Log } \Sigma_{10}$

$|\sigma_{\text{zphot}}| = 0.0336$

Contours at 1 and 3σ above the mean density

Spectroscopic follow-up

VLT/FORS2, VIMOS; MMT/HECTOSPEC

CL1411.1-1148

So far 218 galaxies within 5σ of z_{clus}

The analysis of the galaxy stellar populations is for another talk ...

- Fueling star formation – molecular gas:
SEEDisCS (Spatially extended EDisCS)

ALMA cycle 3 CO(3-2)

17 galaxies observed so far, 36 more to come

ALMA cycle 3 CO(3-2)

Spérone-Longin et al., in prep

17 new galaxies detected in CO at $z=0.5$: 200% increase

small mass cluster LIRG detected at $24\mu\text{m}$ (Spitzer)

17 new galaxies detected in CO at z=0.5 : 200% increase

Nearby galaxies

Jablonka et al., 2013, A&A, 557, 1031

- Galaxy are remarkably resistant – relatively large quenching timescales are needed
- We are on our way to census (in an unbiased way) the molecular content of galaxies still star forming around intermediate redshift galaxy clusters: a step forward in itself and *a zero-point status for higher z studies*
- So far cluster LSS seem to miss the high tail of the cold gas mass distribution as compared to the field